

Supplementary material for
*When internal reconstruction goes further: Proposing the
vowel system of Pre-Khroskyabs through examining bound
state apophony*

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Tables 1 and 2 show non-final vowels that should be reconstructed as *-o^v- and -u-, respectively, which do not show bound states in the modern language.

Table 1. Non-final *-o^v-

First component	Gloss	Second component	Gloss	Compound	Gloss
<i>mô</i>	brother (female speaking)	<i>snóm</i>	sister (male speaking)	<i>mosnóm</i>	brother and sister
<i>só</i>	again	† <i>ke</i>	?	<i>sokê</i>	again
<i>nbô</i>	be deaf	† <i>q^he</i>	NMLZ?	<i>nboq^hé</i>	deaf person
<i>ydó</i>	be poor	<i>zî</i>	son	<i>γdozî</i>	poor person
<i>sqó</i>	<i>Sambucus javanica</i>	<i>ts^həydô</i>	bucket	<i>sqóts^həydo</i>	the fruit of <i>Sambucus javanica</i>
<i>ntsó</i>	vegetable	<i>ré</i>	soup	<i>ntsoré</i>	vegetable soup

Table 2. Non-final *-u-

First component	Gloss	Second component	Gloss	Compound	Gloss
<i>ts^hô</i>	ladder	† <i>k^hroy</i>	?	<i>ts^hək^hrôγ</i>	rung
<i>ynô</i>	sun	<i>fts^hôd</i>	heat	<i>γnəts^hôd</i>	dry in the sun
<i>dzô</i>	skin	<i>p^hæd</i>	abandon	<i>ɛndzôp^hæd</i>	moult
<i>χp^hrô</i>	bear	<i>ɲæɛ</i>	be black	<i>χp^hrôɲæɛ</i>	black bear
<i>k^hô</i>	back	† <i>di</i>	day	<i>k^hədí</i>	two days after tomorrow
<i>snô</i>	day	† <i>go</i>	?	<i>snôgo</i>	noon
<i>χtô</i>	wear (hat)	† <i>lu</i>	?	<i>χtəlu</i>	hat

In Table 3, Pre-Khroskyabs reconstructions are compared to cognates in Xiaoyili Khroskyabs and in Tangut. The column “Corr. Xiaoyili” shows the correspondence of velarisation status between Xiaoyili and Pre-Khroskyabs, marked with a tick if velarity-accordant. The column “Corr. Tangut” shows the correspondence between uvularisation in Tangut and velarisation in either Pre-Khroskyabs and Xiaoyili, marked with tick if accordant.

The Xiaoyili data come from Huang (2007), Sun (2005), and Sun (2008). The Tangut data come from Li (1997).

Table 3. Velarisation in Xiaoyili Khroskyabs and uvularisation in Tangut compared to Pre-Khroskyabs reconstructions

Gloss	Pre-Khroskyabs	Xiaoyili	Tangut	Corr. Xiaoyili	Corr. Tangut
half	*c ^h [ə]	c ^h ə	074 khwə*1	✓	
open	*c ^h o ^v	c ^h o ^v	070 thwi1	✓	
behind	*k ^h [ə]	k ^h ə	2503 qu*1	✓	
ear	*ɲu ^v	ɲu ^v	4681 nu1	✓	
fire	*ɲm[ə]	ɲmə	4408 məə*1, from preinitial	✓	
kill	*sæ ^v d	sə ^v shā	4225 sa1	✓	
ten	*sjud	sjət	1084 ɣa*2	✓	
be thirsty	*svæ(-ɣ)	sví	4532 pa*2	✓	
one	*ræɣ	rəu	100 le ^w	✓	
year	*dyu(ʸ)	djú	3003 ʒu*1	✓	✓
milk	*lu(ʸ)	lú	3065 lhu1	✓	✓
head	*bu(ʸ)	Ɂú	2750 ku*1	✓	✓
human	*vju(ʸ)	vjú	1784 lu*1	✓	✓
old, used	*bæ ^v	bè	923 wə*1	✓	✓
low	*be(-r)	bè	3791 bi2	✓	✓
food	*dzæ	dzi	4517 dzi1	✓	✓
accompany	*f-sn[ɹ]	fɲí	2440 nii2	✓	✓
steal	*fk[ə]	fkə	5817 kwir1	✓	✓
wear	*gæ	gí	5598 gwi2	✓	✓
millstone	*ɣvæ	ɣví	973 ʔwjr2	✓	✓
dog	*katæ ^v	katé	3732 1312 ku*1ta*1	✓	✓
sky	*m[ɹ]	mə ^v	3513 mə*1	✓	✓
breast	*nu ^v or *nu	nəɣ	4614 nu2	✓	✓
bowl	*q ^h [ɹ]	q ^h ú ^v	4189 qhu ^r	✓	✓
face	*rɲæ ^v	rɲè	3158 ɲwə*2	✓	✓
throat	*rɲo ^v	rɲó	458 qo ^r	✓	✓
narrow	*Ɂro ^v	Ɂró	3287 5561 ru*1ra*2	✓	✓
blood	*s[ə]	sá	2734 sij1	✓	✓
road	*tɕæ	tɕí	0020 tɕa1	✓	✓
drink	*t ^h e	t ^h è	4658 thi1	✓	✓
hot	*ts ^h æ(-d)	ts ^h í	1829 tsha1	✓	✓
son	*zæ	zi	2134 zwi1	✓	✓
snake	*bu(ʸ)r	bár	080 phɔ*2	✓	✓
iron	*ɕ[ə](ʸ)m	ʃám ʃám	4995 cow1	✓	✓
louse	*co(ʸ)ɣ	ʃáɹ	5705 aiw2	✓	✓
bend	*go(ʸ)ɣ	gəu	1377 kiwr2	✓	✓
door	*ɣ[ə](ʸ)m	ɣəm	5689 ɳa*2	✓	✓
house	*j[ə](ʸ)m	jəm	2560 ʔji2	✓	✓
hand	*jo(ʸ)ɣ	jóɣ	3485 la*1	✓	✓
waist	*jo(ʸ)ɣ	jəɣ	3087 dziw1	✓	✓
forget	*lmə(ʸ)d	lmə	2325 mji2	✓	✓
leaf	*lp ^h æ(ʸ)ɣ	lp ^h ax	4561 ba*2	✓	✓
smoke	*mk ^h u(ʸ)d	mk ^h ə	3673 yu1	✓	✓
be red	*mnw(ʸ)ɣ	mnəɣ	1671 nij1	✓	✓
be black	*ɲæ(ʸ)ɣ	ɲáɣ	176 naa1	✓	✓
rib	*ɲ[ə](ʸ)m	ɲəm	2857 ɲo*2	✓	✓
hoe	*qæ(ʸ)ɣ	qáɣ	5313 qa*1	✓	✓
hit	*tu(ʸ)l	tál	1899 tu1	✓	✓
alcohol	*vo(ʸ)ɣ	vəɣ	2045 ʔo*2	✓	✓
cloud	*zd[ə](ʸ)m	zdəm	2738 dij2	✓	✓
be sour	*ɕte ^h u(ʸ)r	ɕt ^h ú ^r	2739 tchwir	✓	✓
weave, sew	*dæ ^v ɣ	dèr (typo? dèy)	630 la*1	✓	✓
last night	*ɣmæ ^r	ɣmár	3925 mu*1r1	✓	✓
two	*ɣnæ ^r	ɣné	4027 nii1	✓	✓
be thick	*jæ ^v ɣ	jè	3192 laa*1	✓	✓
1SG	*ɲæC	ɲá	2098 ɲa*2	✓	✓
vomit	*p ^h [æ]z	p ^h éɣ	4585 wa1	✓	✓
pig	*p ^h æ ^v k	p ^h è	294 wa*1	✓	✓
white	*p ^h rə ^v m	p ^h rə ^v m	1572 phɔ*ow1	✓	✓
be spicy	*r[d]zæ ^v	rzáv	045 za*1r1	✓	✓
write	*ræd	rá	1715 rar1	✓	✓
deer	*rtsæz	rtsá	5181 tsa ^r	✓	✓
needle	*ɳæ ^v	ɳáv	4935 ɳa*1	✓	✓
goat	*ts ^h æd	ts ^h á	2367 tshi1	✓	✓
ghost	*dju(ʸ)	djú		✓	
pour	*du(ʸ)	dú		✓	
be wet	*lu(ʸ)	lú		✓	
be hot	*ski(ʸ)	skí		✓	
bake	*vu(ʸ)	vú		✓	
give	*b[ə]	bá		✓	
DEM	*c[ə]	cá		✓	
hybrid of yak and bull	*ɕ[ə]	ɕá		✓	
Tibetan barley	*ɕ[ə]	ɕá		✓	

Table 3 – continued from previous page

Gloss	Pre-Khroskyabs	Xiaoyili	Tangut	Corr. Xiaoyili	Corr. Tangut
contain	*dzɔʷ(-d)	dzóʷ		✓	
hold	*dze	dzé		✓	
available	*goʷ	gúʷ		✓	
water	*yɔ[ə]	yɔ̄		✓	
roll up	*kako	kəkó		✓	
dry in sun	*kʰo	kʰó		✓	
be hungry	*moʷ	mó		✓	
eat (AUTOBEN)	*n-dzæ(-t)	ndzí		✓	
rest	*næ(-t)	ní		✓	
use	*ntɕʰe	ntʰʲé		✓	
hoof	*qæze	qÁtʃu		✓	
rooftop	*rboʷ	rbóʷ		✓	
have	*re	ré		✓	
cause to be small	*s-ze	ldzé		✓	
who	*s[ʷ]	sə		✓	
wildberry	*sæs[ə]	sAsə		✓	
seven	*sp[e]	χspé		✓	
hit	*tsʰ[ʷ]	tsʰə		✓	
salt	*tsʰæ	tsʰí		✓	
serow	*veŋæ	vəŋí		✓	
reduce swelling	*z[ə]	zə		✓	
pond	*d[ə](ʷ)m	dám		✓	
help	*yuu(ʷ)r	yúr		✓	
finish	*jo(ʷ)ɣ	jóu		✓	
be sunken	*j[ə](ʷ)m	jóm		✓	
buckwheat	*muwo(ʷ)ɣ	jəu		✓	
keep secret	*ndzu(ʷ)d	ndzíʷ		✓	
food, CLF	*rgo(ʷ)ɣ	rgəu		✓	
be numerous/explode	*kbo(ʷ)ɣ	kbu		✓	
be clever	*skræ(ʷ)ɣ	sqrəχ		✓	
bean	*sno(ʷ)ɣ	snəuli		✓	
be bitter	*tɕʰæ(ʷ)ɣ	tʰʲəχ		✓	
be fine (not thick)	*ts[ə](ʷ)m	tsəm		✓	
twine	*tuu(ʷ)v	təʷ		✓	
butter	*vuu(ʷ)ɣ	vəu or vəʷ		✓	
female cattle	*vzu(ʷ)ɣ	vzəʷ		✓	
be short	*xtuu(ʷ)z	xɰ		✓	
be sharp	*zo(ʷ)ɣ	zəu		✓	
Solanum muricatum	*zo(ʷ)ɣ	zəu		✓	
collide	*χtɕʰuu(ʷ)d	χtʰʲə		✓	
fall	*boʷz	bóʷ		✓	
early, before	*dzuy	dzəu		✓	
foot	*gæʷv	gəʷ		✓	
be flat	*yɔ̄æʷv	yɔ̄əʷ		✓	
release (Stem 2)	*lid	lí		✓	
tonight	*mæɣ	mAr		✓	
dip	*mnoɣ	mnoʷχ		✓	
suck	*ndzɣəʷv	ndzɣəʷ		✓	
bite	*nrcʰæʷd	nrcʰá		✓	
laugh	*qʰæd	qʰá qʰÁ		✓	
say	*ræʷz	rəʷ rə		✓	
be wide	*rjəʷm	rjəʷm		✓	
heart	*sjæʷr	sjər		✓	
moon	*snoyl[ʷ]	snəuli		✓	
be narrow	*tsræz	tsrə		✓	
mix	*vzjær	vzjAr		✓	
summer	*vzæʷr	vzər		✓	
badger	*xpæz	xpə		✓	
six	*xtɕo(-ɣ)	xɰjə		✓	
porridge	*zbroʷ	zbrúʷ		✓	

References

- Huang, Bufan. 2007. *Lawurongyu yanjiu* (拉坞戎语研究) [Study on the Lavrung language]. Beijing: Nationalities Press.
- Li, Fanwen. 1997. *Xia-Han zidian* 夏漢字典 [Tangut-Chinese dictionary]. Beijing: China Social Sciences Press, (李範文).
- Sun, Jackson T.-S. 2008. Tonality in Caodeng rGgyalrong. In Huber, Brigitte, Marianne Volkart & Paul Widmer (eds.), *Chomolangma, Demawend und Kasbek: Festschrift für*

- Roland Bielmeier zu Seinem 65 Geburtstag*, 257–280. Halle (Saale): International Institute for Tibetan and Buddhist Studies.
- Sun, T.-S., Jackson. 2005. Linguistic coding of generic human arguments in rGyalrongic languages. Paper presented at the 11th Himalayan Languages Symposium. Bangkok: Chulalongkorn University.